

FOSTERING DIVERSITY: EXPLORING THE EXPERIENCES OF SELECTED INDIGENOUS PEOPLE APPOINTED IN LEADERSHIP POSITIONS IN GOVERNMENT INSTITUTIONS USING THE GLASS CLIFF THEORY⁵

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the experiences of Indigenous people concerning the glass cliff phenomenon. The glass cliff refers to a phenomenon where individuals from marginalized or underrepresented groups are more likely to be appointed to leadership positions during times of crisis or instability. While previous studies have primarily focused on gender-related glass cliffs, this study sheds light on Indigenous individuals' experiences in similar circumstances. The research aims to understand the impact of the glass cliff on indigenous individuals, examining both negative and positive experiences. Qualitative research methodology, specifically descriptive phenomenology, was employed to explore the lived experiences of Indigenous individuals who have encountered the glass cliff. Six Indigenous respondents were selected through purposive sampling, ensuring diverse experiences and perspectives. In-depth interviews were conducted to gather rich and detailed accounts of their experiences. The findings of this study revealed that Indigenous individuals face the glass cliff phenomenon, experiencing an increased likelihood of being appointed to leadership positions during challenges or crises. However, the study also uncovered a surprising aspect: the glass cliff can provide positive experiences for Indigenous individuals. Despite the inherent challenges, some participants viewed their leadership positions as opportunities. Overall, this research contributes to the understanding of the glass cliff phenomenon from the perspective of indigenous individuals. The study highlights the unique challenges indigenous leaders face when placed in leadership positions during times of crisis. Additionally, it uncovers the potential for positive outcomes, demonstrating Indigenous individuals' resilience, determination, and ability to navigate and leverage the glass cliff to make meaningful contributions. The findings emphasized recognizing and supporting Indigenous leadership within organizations to create more equitable and inclusive environments

Keywords: Glass Cliff, Leadership Position, Indigenous People, Experiences

INTRODUCTION

The Glass Cliff phenomenon is a captivating and thought-provoking concept that sheds light on the experiences of Indigenous People in leadership positions in times of challenges within the organization. There has been a growing recognition of the importance of diversity and inclusion within government institutions worldwide in recent years. One key aspect of this movement is the empowerment and representation of indigenous peoples in leadership positions. Building upon the well-known metaphor of the glass ceiling, which represents the invisible barriers that prevent marginalized groups from advancing to the top posts, Glass Cliff refers specifically to the precarious situations Indigenous People often find themselves in when they break through these barriers.

Expanding on the widely recognized idea of the glass ceiling, which symbolizes the unseen barriers hindering marginalized groups from reaching top positions, the concept of the Glass Cliff relates explicitly to the vulnerable situations often faced by Indigenous People when they manage to break through these barriers. This notion was initially introduced in 2004 by Michelle Ryan and Alex Haslam, who noticed a clear trend in appointing women to leadership roles. They observed that women were more likely to be placed in such positions during times of crisis or when the organization was already in a precarious state (Business Insider, 2020). The glass cliff phenomenon is a well-supported concept backed by research, whereby an individual from an underrepresented background is promoted to a high-level leadership position when the likelihood of failure is significantly elevated

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(Ward, 2022). In essence, the term "glass cliff" refers to a situation where a woman or a member of a minority group assumes a leadership role in challenging circumstances, posing a high risk of failure.

Furthermore, an additional study conducted by a researcher revealed that Indigenous People also face the Glass Cliff phenomenon, which emphasizes the extra obstacles and dangers encountered by individuals belonging to underrepresented racial or ethnic groups. In 2013, Alison Cook and Christy Glass from Utah State University discovered that the glass cliff phenomenon was widespread among people of color assuming leadership roles (Slater, 2020). This phenomenon uncovered a troubling pattern: Marginalized individuals were appointed to high-level positions precisely when the likelihood of failure was exceptionally high.

The consequences of the Glass Cliff are multifaceted. On the other hand, minority leaders may be viewed as symbols of diversity and progress, providing inspiration and breaking stereotypes; however, their appointment to high-risk positions could also create an environment where success is complex, making it harder for them to overcome the hurdles and thrive in their roles. As Kagan (2022) noted, when the position is risky, the company will likely experience difficulty in management. The glass cliff sets up Indigenous People leaders for potential failure. The conditions of their appointment being placed in challenging or unstable leadership positions can create additional challenges that make managing people more difficult.

This phenomenon presents significant challenges for Indigenous individuals, making it extremely difficult to establish an inclusive work environment. It erects barriers that hinder the success of Indigenous individuals in their leadership careers, and even if these barriers are overcome, there is a risk of encountering false inclusion. This issue prompted the decision to conduct research in this area. Currently, there is a need for more studies that specifically focus on the experience of Indigenous People in organizations concerning the glass cliff. Originally used to describe the struggles women face in attaining leadership positions, there is also a need for more research exploring the situation of Indigenous People within governmental institutions. This knowledge gap motivated the undertaking of this research.

This lack of recognition further undermines the situations of Indigenous people in such leadership roles within government institutions. In light of this, the researcher decided to investigate the status of Indigenous People in leadership positions within government institutions and gain a comprehensive understanding of the causes and effects of the Glass Cliff phenomenon on Indigenous individuals and within the government institution itself.

This study aims to provide a solid foundation for policymakers and decision-making bodies in organizations to develop actions and policies that promote ethnic diversity, inclusion, and more effective representation of Indigenous People. Additionally, the study seeks to prevent their exploitation, promote decent work, and economic growth, reduce inequalities among Indigenous People, and strengthen institutions. Although the body of empirical research on the glass cliff phenomenon is still in its early stages, this research aims to develop a cohesive body of evidence confirming its existence and significance. The researchers also identified key concepts that require further investigation and outlined potential practical applications of their findings to promote equality and diversity in governmental institutions.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this study aimed to understand the experiences of selected Indigenous people in Isabela working in government institutions regarding their leadership appointment or promotion. The research design chosen was descriptive phenomenology, which provided insights into subjective experiences and challenged assumptions. Respondents were selected purposively from the Ybanag and Yogad ethnic groups, totaling six individuals, as they represented smaller Indigenous people populations in Isabela. A semi-structured interview guide was utilized as the research instrument, divided into five parts to investigate various aspects such as factors influencing appointments, effects of glass cliff experiences, coping strategies, and the identification of actions and policies for inclusiveness. Data gathering involved initial interviews, validation of the guide questions, and one-on-one interviews with the respondents, with their consent obtained for audio recordings. Thematic data analysis was used to interpret the interview results, facilitating a deeper understanding of respondents' views and experiences. Ethical considerations were addressed by ensuring informed consent, discussing privacy and confidentiality, and submitting the research paper for evaluation by supervisors and external examiners.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Perceived Factors of Indigenous People Influencing Their Appointment to Leadership Positions within Government Institutions

Understanding the factors contributing to the glass cliff phenomenon is of utmost importance in addressing the challenges faced by individuals, particularly those from marginalized groups, when assuming leadership roles. Most respondents answered that they think one of the reasons for their appointment to a challenging leadership position is their capabilities, such as being dedicated, committed, trustworthy, and confident in their work (A. Mabini, Written Communication, May 14, 2023). As narrated by other respondents. *"Out of trustworthy, yun yung nabanggit ng anak ni mayor, na 'tita kaya po kayo pinaupo ni papa is out of trustworthy... Binigay niya saakin yung ano e yung trust. alam niyang kakayanin ko at nakayanan ko naman awa ng diyos. Napanindigan ko naman yung tiwala ng ibinigay saakin."* "Out of trustworthy, that is what the mayor's child mentioned, saying, 'Auntie, that reason why dad made you sit is out of trustworthy... He gave me what, you know, the trust. He knew that I could handle it, and I could endure it through God's mercy. I stood by the trust given to me" (G. Del Pilar, Personal Communication, April 28, 2023). On the other hand, another respondent expressed, *"Dahil ako ay eligible at sa work experience kaya ako ang napili sa position na iyon."* (Because I am eligible and have the work experience, that's why I was chosen for that position) (A. Mabini, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023).

This implies that the respondents' track records and demonstrated abilities in specific areas of governance or expertise played a role in their appointment to leadership positions. In line with the glass cliff theory, individuals with a strong track record of working experience may be seen as competent in handling difficult situations. Their past successes and experiences can make them attractive candidates for leadership roles, especially when addressing organizational crises or challenges is necessary. As supported by Khush (n.d.), Their expertise and proven capabilities make them stand out as candidates capable of navigating complex situations.

Condition of Indigenous People's Appointment

To explore the glass cliff phenomenon, the researchers examined the circumstances surrounding respondents' appointments. One respondent unexpectedly assumed a leadership role due to a sudden vacancy caused by the previous officer's death, intensifying the challenges faced. Similarly, another respondent was chosen after the intended candidates withdrew due to the demanding accountability associated with the position, deviating from the original plan. Additionally, frequent resignations and the reluctance of others to assume the role due to its sensitive nature also influenced appointments. Furthermore, two respondents were appointed during the early stages of a new office, characterized by limited resources and uncertainty. These findings illuminate the glass cliff, where marginalized individuals face challenges in leadership roles during crises or transitions, aligning with the glass cliff theory (Kagan, 2022).

Experiences of Indigenous People being Appointed to Leadership Positions within Government Institutions when Problems Arise

The experiences of Indigenous people being appointed to leadership positions in government institutions encompass both negative and positive aspects. among the negative experiences reported by respondents are difficulties in managing people, feelings of self-doubt and uncertainty, inadequate equipment and other resources, difficulties in managing paper effectively, being subjected to scrutiny from others, inadequate training and seminars for professional development, insufficient number of human resources, delayed approval of the budget. furthermore, one respondent expressed her struggles in managing subordinates and highlighted the challenges of managing people within the office (A. Gabriela, Personal Communication, May 14, 2023). Also, another respondent expressed feelings of unhappiness and self-doubt, as they believed someone else should have taken the position, indicating a lack of confidence and uncertainty in their role as a leader (G. Del Pilar, personal communication, April 28, 2023). Moreover, one respondent stated, "My boss scolded me once, and I admit that I was wrong.

"Paperwork in government institutions is sometimes not easy to deal with. Especially when it comes to receiving letters, I may inevitably overlook some of them." (J. Zamora, written information, May 14, 2023). One of the respondents, the head of MENRO, shared that they needed more equipment and resources to do their job. (E. Aguinaldo Personal communication, May 02, 2023) On the other hand, one individual shared that she encountered scrutiny and questioning regarding their compliance with program regulations, necessitating an investigation and audit to prove their adherence to the correct procedures." (A. Gabriela, telephone communication, May 14, 2023). Furthermore, one respondent highlighted the absence of training opportunities before assuming their position,

indicating a lack of support for professional growth and development. Inadequate Training and Seminars for Professional Development (G. Del Pilar, personal communication, April 28, 2023). One of the respondents also mentioned, *"Dito sa office namin, kulang talaga kami sa tao kaya madalas naoverwork."* (In our office, we are understaffed, so we often end up overworking) (A. Mabini, written communication, May 02, 2023). It was also highlighted that being in a challenging leadership position, one of the respondents also shared that she faced delays in planning and organizing activities due to the initial lack of budget approval, conflicts in scheduling, and the absence of necessary legal documents required for the approval process. (A. Gabriela, Phonecall Communication, May 14, 2023)

These negative experiences are true with the account of Kagan (2022) saying that the glass cliff phenomenon presents a distressing and seemingly insurmountable predicament, as individuals find themselves placed in positions where failure becomes almost inevitable. These circumstances occur within work environments that are specifically designed to challenge and impede the success of those who face these obstacles. Therefore, this supports the understanding that the glass cliff creates an unjust and difficult situation for individuals who surpass these obstacles. This experience proves that Indigenous leaders appointed in government institutions often face a range of challenges and negative experiences, as revealed by the findings of the study. This supports the assumption of Cook and Glass (2013) that Indigenous people remain underrepresented in positions of authority because of barriers such as discrimination, biases, racial tokenism, and exclusion from social and informational networks.

On the other side of the coin, the glass cliff phenomenon, often associated with posing risks to Indigenous people, can also yield positive experiences for Indigenous people. One example is achieving professional growth. One individual acknowledges that encountering and solving problems in their leadership role can be seen as an opportunity for personal and professional growth. They recognize the value of learning from these challenges and acquiring problem-solving skills, which contribute to their development as a professional. *"Syempre kung papaano ko isolve yung problema. yung matutunan mo."* (In reality, it becomes a problem for me if I don't see it as a benefit, especially in figuring out how to solve the problem. That is what you will learn.) (E. Aguinaldo, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023). Another positive experience they had was having financial benefits. One respondent highlights the financial benefits associated with their leadership position. They indicate that their salary is higher compared to other jobs, suggesting that the position offers financial incentives and better compensation compared to alternative employment opportunities. (A. Gabriela, Telephone Communication, May 14, 2023).

Contrary to the commonly perceived risks associated with the glass cliff phenomenon, it is noteworthy that Indigenous individuals may also encounter positive experiences in such leadership roles. One of the positive aspects highlighted is the potential for professional growth. This entails viewing the challenges faced as opportunities for personal and career development, enabling individuals to acquire problem-solving skills and expand their expertise. By embracing and learning from these experiences, Indigenous leaders can enhance their professional capabilities.

Additionally, financial benefits can be a positive outcome of occupying a glass cliff position. One respondent emphasized the higher salary associated with their leadership role compared to other jobs. This suggests that such positions offer improved financial incentives and better compensation, providing individuals with economic advantages.

This analysis acknowledges that, despite the inherent challenges and risks, the glass cliff phenomenon can also provide Indigenous people with avenues for personal and professional growth, as well as financial benefits. It highlights the importance of recognizing and appreciating the potential positive aspects of this complex phenomenon.

Effects of Glass Cliff Phenomenon on Indigenous People

The experiences recounted by the respondents define the impacts of the glass cliff phenomenon on Indigenous individuals. These effects have been explicitly outlined by the respondents as follows: not being able to achieve set goals and inability to finish the task within the set deadline. Not Producing Quality Outputs, Feelings of Disappointment from Subordinates/ Higher authorities, Ability to Address Problems within the Institutions, Opportunity to Become a Leader.

Upon the Indigenous people's appointment to challenging leadership positions. The results revealed that as an effect of being exposed to glass cliff some respondents were not able to achieve set goals within their

organization "Noong una nahihirapan ako sa pag achieve ng goals dito, kasi nag levelup yung work ko, dapat talagang magsumikap para magawa ko ng maayos yung trabaho." (At first, I struggled to achieve goals here because my work leveled up. I had to exert effort to do my job well.) (G. Del Pilar, Personal Communication, April 28, 2023). The glass cliff phenomenon presents specific challenges and barriers for indigenous people leaders, which hinder their capacity to accomplish predetermined objectives.

Furthermore, as they are often appointed during difficult times or challenging situations, it becomes arduous for them to complete assigned tasks or achieve set goals within a specified timeframe "*Kapag bombarded ako ng paper works, nahihirapan talaga ako. Dun na pumapasok yung mali mali kong entries.*" (When I get bombarded with paperwork, I really struggle. That is when my mistakes in entries come into play.) (J. Zamora, Personal Communication, May 14) The demanding responsibilities inherent in leadership positions, coupled with the unique pressures experienced by Indigenous people, can generate a stressful atmosphere that detrimentally affects their capacity to produce high-quality work. The anxiety of potential failure, the necessity to challenge stereotypes, and the burden of disproving negative assumptions can further erode their confidence and lead to a decline in the standard of their output. The additional pressure to demonstrate their worth in challenging leadership roles can create a stress-inducing environment that impedes their performance and diminishes the caliber of their work (Graham, 2022). Some respondents also expressed that when they make mistakes or fail to succeed in fulfilling their roles it cannot be helped that some of their subordinates or higher authorities show disappointment in them (G. Del Pilar, Personal Communication, April 28, 2023).

This result implies that the glass cliff phenomenon poses specific challenges and barriers for Indigenous people leaders, impacting their ability to achieve set goals within their organizations. The results indicate that these leaders often struggle to fulfill their responsibilities and face increased pressure when appointed during challenging times. This leads to difficulties in completing assigned tasks and meeting objectives within specified time frames. The combination of demanding leadership roles, additional pressures faced by Indigenous people, and the fear of failure can create a stressful environment that hinders their performance and diminishes the quality of their work. Furthermore, when mistakes or failures occur, some respondents mentioned experiencing disappointment from their subordinates or higher authorities. It also supports the statement of Oakes (2022) that while those glass cliff positions can provide a way for some leaders to prove themselves, they come with significant downsides.

From a different perspective, it was discovered in this study that the glass cliff phenomenon could also incorporate positive effects. It was revealed in this study that some indigenous people may use this as an opportunity to rise to the occasion, leveraging their skills, experiences, and perspectives to navigate and overcome challenges. (A. Bonifacio, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023) This indicates the leader's awareness of the complexities of managing a team. It demonstrates their ability to handle interpersonal issues diplomatically and promote a harmonious working environment. In addition, the glass cliff phenomenon also provided an avenue for indigenous people, such as indigenous people, to assume leadership roles they may not have otherwise been considered for. (A. Gabriela, Phone call Communication, May 14, 2023) This perspective suggests a positive effect of the Glass Cliff phenomenon in providing underrepresented groups, such as Indigenous people, the chance to assume leadership roles.

Strategies of Indigenous People to Cope with Challenges Caused by the Glass Cliff Phenomenon

Implemented programs and activities to avoid the glass cliff phenomenon

The prevalence of negative experiences and their impact on Indigenous individuals highlights the need for effective coping mechanisms to address the challenges of the glass cliff phenomenon. These are the identified specific strategies to navigate these adverse aspects of the glass cliff, including: Developing a Comprehensive Understanding of the Role and Responsibilities, Build Resilience and Adaptability to Challenges, Collaborate with Co-Employees, Attentiveness to Details on the Tasks Assigned, Delegate Work Responsibilities, Effective Record Management, Negotiate for Resources to Navigate the Challenges of Glass Cliff, Demonstrate Passion for Work, adopt a Proactive Mindset when Dealing with Challenges in the Workplace, Facilitating Open Dialogue and Encouraging Constructive Feedback.

One respondent noted that in order to avoid challenges posed by glass cliff, "*Pag-aralan ang posisyon, ano ang sakop ng trabaho at paano ito mapagbuti, at maging productive.*" (Study the position, understand the scope of work, and find ways to improve and be productive.) (A. Mabini, Written Communication, May 02, 2023) Another respondent also expressed that Resilience is essential for leaders in challenging positions, as it enables

them to handle added pressures, scrutiny, and potential failures. By believing in themselves, continuously learning, addressing mistakes, and staying focused on their convictions, individuals can navigate the glass cliff and inspire others to do the same (A. Gabriela, Phone Call Communication, May 14, 2023). Moreover, collaborating with co-employees can also be essential in coping with this phenomenon (A. Bonifacio, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023). In addition, being attentive to details also enables individuals to avoid misunderstandings, produce high-quality work, and meet task requirements and expectations (A. Mabini, Written Communication, May 02, 2023). Another respondent expressed that Effective leadership involves delegating responsibilities and relying on the support and involvement of team members. By distributing leadership and tasks, leaders can tap into their team's diverse skills and expertise, fostering a collaborative work environment and achieving collective goals (A. Bonifacio, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023).

One of the respondents also emphasizes the importance of maintaining proper records for their workloads. They acknowledge that it is inevitable for some papers to go missing during the process, but by having a systematic record-keeping approach, they can trace the whereabouts of the documents and know where they last had them (A. Mabini, Written Communication, May 02, 2023). It was also elicited from the answers of respondents that it is important to advocate for and secure the necessary resources, such as training, seminars, and capable staff, to enhance preparedness and effectiveness in leadership positions. This was supported by *How to Identify and Avoid the Glass Cliff as a Female Executive*, KeyBank, 2018. Discover the available support systems by investigating the existing infrastructure. By prioritizing both financial and social resources, individuals can increase their chances of success (G. Del Pilar, Personal Communication, April 28, 2023). Moreover, showing genuine enthusiasm and dedication to tasks and goals is crucial for job satisfaction and fulfillment. Loving and respecting one's job, as well as valuing colleagues, fosters a positive work environment and contributes to individual and organizational success (E. Aguinaldo, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023).

Furthermore, Recognizing and acknowledging the challenges and inconsistencies that come with the glass cliff is important. Taking a practical and proactive approach to problem-solving allows leaders to address issues promptly and maintain a healthy work environment (A. Bonifacio, Personal communication, May 02, 2023). In addition, creating an environment that promotes open dialogue and constructive feedback fosters collaboration, innovation, and personal growth. By engaging in open communication and understanding the strengths and weaknesses of colleagues, leaders can build strong relationships and address conflicts effectively (E. Aguinaldo, Personal Communication, May 02, 2023). Lastly, intentionally fostering strong, respectful, and collaborative connections with colleagues and the broader organizational family is crucial. Building positive relationships creates a supportive work environment where individuals can work together effectively towards shared goals, ultimately enhancing teamwork and outcomes

Building Positive Relationships within the Workplace

While the above-mentioned challenges were recognized by the respondents and proved true to the effect that comes with a glass cliff, it is unfortunate that they were unable to identify specific programs or strategies aimed at addressing the glass cliff phenomenon. This lack of identification may be attributed to the fact that the glass cliff phenomenon still needs to be fully recognized and understood by institutions, resulting in a lack of awareness and knowledge surrounding this phenomenon. As Dorsey (2023) asserts, deciding how to navigate a glass cliff begins with recognizing you are facing one. In essence, the inability to discern targeted programs, activities, and other approaches for addressing the glass cliff can be attributed to a failure to comprehensively recognize and comprehend this phenomenon within institutional contexts.

Furthermore, the respondents acknowledged the absence of any implemented initiatives within their organization specifically designed to address the glass cliff phenomenon. Despite their inability to provide a list of programs aimed at circumventing the glass cliff, some respondents expressed a willingness to embrace demanding leadership roles. Rather than avoiding such positions altogether, their desire was focused on mitigating the challenges associated with the glass cliff (A. Gabriela, Phone Call Communication, May 14, 2023) (J. Zamora, Personal Communication, May 14, 2023). A glass cliff is a harsh and unfortunate reality, but it does not have to remain so. That does not mean you should forfeit opportunities just because a company is struggling (Key Bank, n.d.).

Overall, the analysis underscores the need for institutions to deepen their understanding and recognition of the Glass Cliff phenomenon. It emphasizes the importance of developing comprehensive and targeted

programs, activities, and approaches to effectively address the challenges it presents. Moreover, it highlights the respondents' proactive approach in embracing leadership roles despite the glass cliff, signifying a desire to overcome adversities rather than evade responsibility. By acknowledging the glass cliff phenomenon and implementing suitable measures, institutions can create an inclusive and supportive environment that enables individuals to navigate and thrive in challenging leadership positions.

CONCLUSION

Through extensive research, it has become evident that a distinctive form of bias exists within leadership positions of government organizations. The study revealed various factors that influenced the appointment of Indigenous people in leadership positions. Notably, beliefs about their personal capabilities and prior work experience were identified as additional contributing factors. Furthermore, the findings suggest that Indigenous People leaders encounter difficulties when navigating challenging leadership roles. These difficulties encompass managing people, experiencing self-doubt and uncertainty, lack of necessary resources, inefficient paperwork management, scrutiny from others, inadequate training and professional development opportunities, insufficient human resources, and delayed budget approvals. However, alongside these challenges, positive experiences were also reported, such as professional growth and financial incentives. These results indicate that while Indigenous people face struggles related to the glass cliff phenomenon, they can also derive positive experiences from such appointments.

Moreover, the study provides an intriguing perspective on the reality of the glass cliff theory. The findings offer evidence supporting the existence of adverse effects and experiences for Indigenous people in challenging leadership positions, confirming the validity of the glass cliff concept. These negative effects may include struggles, limited support and resources, heightened scrutiny, and potential obstacles to success.

However, it is crucial to acknowledge the other side of the coin. The study reveals that the glass cliff can also yield positive effects and experiences for Indigenous people. Contrary to the assumption that they are destined to fail in challenging leadership roles, the research shows that some individuals not only endure but thrive in such circumstances. These leaders seize the opportunities the glass cliff presents, overcome obstacles, and succeed in their positions.

Another significant conclusion drawn from the study is the need for programs or initiatives specifically addressing the glass cliff phenomenon within government institutions. This observation suggests that the existence of glass cliffs has yet to be widely recognized or acknowledged in these organizations. The absence of specific programs indicates a lack of awareness and understanding regarding the challenges faced by marginalized individuals appointed to leadership positions during times of organizational challenges or high-risk situations. This lack of recognition is concerning, as it implies that government institutions may have failed to implement targeted measures or policies to proactively address the glass cliff and mitigate its potential negative effects. By neglecting to recognize and address the glass cliff, these institutions inadvertently perpetuate biases and systemic barriers that hinder marginalized individuals' career progression and success.

In conclusion, the findings of this study support the understanding that the glass cliff is a complex and multifaceted concept. It acknowledges the negative effects and experiences Indigenous people face in challenging leadership positions while highlighting the potential for growth and success. By recognizing and addressing the challenges associated with the glass cliff, organizations can strive to create more inclusive and supportive environments that empower all individuals to thrive in leadership roles, irrespective of their background or identity.

It is important to note that the findings of a single study should be considered partial proof against the glass cliff theory. The theory is based on broader patterns and trends observed in organizational settings. While this study challenges the theory's predictions, further research is necessary to fully understand the experiences of Indigenous people leaders and their likelihood of success or failure in challenging leadership positions.

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